

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Deliverable D8.2

WP	8	Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Data Management
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Dissemination level¹	PU	Delivery date	11/12/2020
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Lead beneficiary	AMADE-UdG
Contributing beneficiaries	UPORTO, e-Xstream

Topic manager approval	Name, date and signature
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Grant agreement No. 864723

¹Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

Project Number: 864723

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Project Acronym: TREAL

Project Title: Thermoplastic material allowable generation using a reliability based virtual modelling platform

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Update of the DMP record

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01	21/04/2020	Initial version	Aravind Sasikumar (AMADE-UDG)	Albert Turon (AMADE-UDG)
02	22/10/2020	Updated version with partners feedback	Aravind Sasikumar (AMADE-UDG) Francisco Pires (UPORTO) Laurent Adam (eX-stream)	Albert Turon (AMADE-UDG)

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No. 864723. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union.

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Executive Summary

This document, D8.2. Data Management Plan (DMP) is a deliverable of the TREAL project launched under the ITD, which is funded by the European Union's H2020 through Clean Sky 2 Programme under the Grant agreement 864723. The overall objective of TREAL is to '*develop an efficient and comprehensive framework to generate material allowables for thermoplastic based composite materials: from the material characterization to the generation of the virtual generation of design allowables*'. This objective is in line to address the development of a material modelling platform for thermoplastic material used for multi-functional thermoplastic fuselages. The global impact of TREAL is to support the aircraft design by reducing or even replacing the physical exhausting structural tests by numerical analysis, thereby a considerable reduction in the cost and time of the design process.

The global objective of TREAL is based on mainly three different key enablers: (a) Appropriate test campaigns and data reduction methods to obtain the material parameters needed to feed the analysis models; (b) reliable analysis models that are able to predict all damage and failure modes at both material and component levels and (c) efficient uncertainty quantification and management methodologies to obtain reliable material and design allowables using analysis models.

Research data that compromise the commercialisation prospects or confidentiality terms will not be made available to public, and hence will be preserved under closed access terms within the members of the consortium. The rest of the research data will be deposited in an open access repository.

The expected type of research data that will be generated along the progress of TREAL project will fall into the following categories: (a) Material manufacturing; (b) Specimen testing; (c) development of analysis models; (d) Uncertainty quantification and management methodologies; (e) Virtual platform generation for material allowable.

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1. DATA MANAGEMENT AND RESPONSIBILITY

1.1. DMP Internal Consortium Policy

The responsibilities associated to the data management plan will be managed by a specific person per each consortium partner, and the overall responsibility of the data management will be managed by the lead beneficiary of the project. The TREAL project coordinator, University of Girona, will be responsible for adopting and procuring a strategy for the data maintenance, selecting a repository for data handling, uploading the data and ensuring that data is kept up to date. The project coordinator will also be responsible entity for all the relations and communications with the topic manager. The different members of the consortium and the responsible contact for each partner are listed below:

Members of TREAL Consortium & responsible contacts

Organization	Role	Responsible Contact
Universitat de Girona (UDG) Placa Sant Domenec 3, Girona, Spain 17004	Coordinator	Project Coordinator: Dr. Albert Turon
Universidade do Porto (UPORTO) Praca Gomes Teixeira, Porto, Portugal 4099 002	Beneficiary	Contact: Dr. Francisco M.A. Pires
MSC Software Belgium S.A. (e-Xstream engineering) Rue Emile Francqui 9 Axis Park, Mont Saint Guibert, Belgium 1435	Beneficiary	Contact: Dr. Laurent Adam
Airbus France	Topic Manager	Contact: Melanie Herman

1.2. Data Management Responsible

The project data contact (PDC) will be responsible and in charge of the data management, uploading, maintenance, and updating. The details of the PDC are given below:

Project Data Contact Responsible

Project Data Contact (PDC)	Dr. Albert Turon
PDC Affiliation	University of Girona
PDC mail	albert.turon@udg.edu
PDC telephone number	+34 673004625

1.3. Data nature, link with previous data and potential users

TREAL project involves manufacturing and experimental testing of thermoplastic composite materials, development of numerical finite element analysis methods with constitutive damage models and generation of uncertainty quantification of the material allowable design values. Hence, this will lead to the generation of experimental raw data (text files, spreadsheets, images, videos), numerical simulation models (numerical data, FEM data) and software implementation of the associated algorithms. The data generated will be used by the other consortium partners to progress on achieving the project objectives. The generated experimental data will be used for the development of reliable analysis models that can predict the response of the material. The analysis models will be utilized for the uncertainty management and quantification and these both will be integrated to develop virtual platform for generating material design allowables. The different sets of generated data will be delivered to the topic manager. Scientific publications, strictly following the agreement of the topic manager and the other partners of the consortium, published in open access journals will be used by the scientific community and the industries.

1.4. Data Summary

The global objective of the TREAL project is divided into sub-objectives and will be realised through the following work packages:

- **WP1:** Thermoplastic specimen manufacturing
- **WP2:** Test campaign for material characterization and design allowable
- **WP3:** Novel thermoplastic material damage and failure model
- **WP4:** Parametric coupon models creation for virtual material and design allowable generation
- **WP5:** Uncertainty quantification and management for virtual design allowable
- **WP6:** Platform for generation of thermoplastic material virtual allowable
- **WP7:** Project management
- **WP8:** Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and data management

The purpose of data generation is to accomplish the above sub-objectives of the TREAL project and the collected data from a particular work package is fed as input to another work package, as shown in the table below:

Work Package	Lead beneficiary	Input data	Output data
WP1	UPORTO	-	Manufactured specimen data
WP2	UDG	Output data from WP1	Experimental results raw data
WP3	UPORTO	Output data from WP2	Material damage model data
WP4	MSC	Output data from WP2, WP3	FEM coupon model data
WP5	UDG	Output data from WP2, WP3, WP4	Virtual design allowable data through UQM
WP6	MSC	Output data from WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	Virtual tool data
WP7	UDG	-	Project management data
WP8	UDG	Output data from WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	DMP report,

			Dissemination and communication plan
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The project will generate data in various fields, as specified in the annexes. The table below presents a global summary of the nature of data generated, type of files and their formats and the corresponding work package in which they are generated.

Nature of Data	Type of file	Standards	Work Package
Specimen manufacturing data	Text Cad files	.doc, .pdf, .DWG	WP1
Experimental raw results data	Text Images Video files Spreadsheet	.doc, .pdf, .txt .jpg, .tif, .png .MP4, .xlsx .csv	WP2
FEM & virtual tool data	Text Abaqus files Scripts Software	.txt, .doc, .pdf .inp, .odb .f, .py .exe	WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6

TREAL project will use the data available within the consortium members such as in-house tools or software, and from standards or published open source scientific data in view of defining the experimental procedures, generating the state-of-the-art review etc.

The main origin of the bulk data generated during TREAL project will be from the experimental tests campaign results, FEM data, coded scripts. The expected size of the data is estimated to be around 20 TB.

In terms of data utility, the first target is the consortium partners who will use the data to fulfil the sub-objectives defined in the work packages. During the project dissemination stage, the scientific publications and conference proceedings (generated after strictly following the dissemination terms mentioned by the TM) will be utilized by the scientific community and industries to further extend the knowledge on the topic and to speed up the innovation.

2. FAIR Data

Following the guidelines on the data management on Horizon 2020, TREAL project partners will ensure that the research data generated is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All the open data (data that will be shared between the consortium partners) will be deposited in the Zenodo multi-disciplinary repository. All data shared in Zenodo is assigned a Digital Object identifiers that allows to identify and locate the data very easily. All the internal data (data that are accessible only to the responsible partner of the consortium) produced will be stored within the institutional repositories.

The following naming convention will be followed by all the partners: '*Projectname_Workpackagenumber_ResponsiblePartner_Filename_versionnumber_Date(yyyymmdd)*'. So for example, the data management plan will be saved as 'TREAL_WP8_AMADEUDG_DMP_v2_20201022'.

All TREAL results deposited in Zenodo repository will provide search keywords along with metadata. For data stored in internal repositories, metadata records will be saved using a spreadsheet that explains the data name, a brief description and the keywords that help to locate them easily.

All the data stored in Zenodo will use DOI versioning and this allows to update a dataset even after publishing. Zenodo handles the updated version numbers of these data sets. The data set stored in the internal repositories will be updated with the new version number using the 'vx' convention, where x is the new version number. In the final version of the document, this will be changed to 'vfinal'. A supporting document that tracks the different versions will be created.

Relevant metadata helps to facilitate the open access to data within the consortium members and to maintain organized data sets. Zenodo repository provides the following deposition metadata fields: title of data, description, files, type of upload, publication date, licence, DOI, keywords, relatable identifiers etc. Metadata for each record is indexed and can be searched directly in Zenodo's search engine after publishing.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Data generated from the work packages 1 to 7 are defined under the confidential dissemination level and hence will be available only within the consortium members. Nevertheless, during the course of the project if any data is intended to be shared, it will be decided between the partners and the topic manager. All the data related to the work package 8 that deals with data management and dissemination plan will be openly available.

The data that has to be made public will be available through the Zenodo repository under open license terms.

All the public data generated will be in widely accepted standard formats and hence no specific tools or software is needed. Majority of the private data can also be accessed without any specific tools.

The default repository for TREAL project is Zenodo. It is a European commission co-funded multi-disciplinary repository for data. A DOI is provided to the data uploaded and file versioning is also possible. Appropriate data links can be sent to other members to access the files, and different levels of restricted access are offered in Zenodo. Zenodo is compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon 2020.

The restricted data in Zenodo will not be available for public and sharing will be possible only under the approval of the depositor of the original file. Data can also be stored with an embargo period, where the data will be restricted until the end of the embargo period and will be public after this period.

2.3. Making data interoperable

The data produced in the TREAL project is interoperable between the different consortium members of the project. As explained before, the output of some work packages from a partner is fed an input to another work package by another partner. Most of the data produced during the project will be of standard widely accepted formats such as Pdf files, Microsoft word files, Microsoft excel sheets, python codes etc.

The metadata vocabularies will be as per the standard default metadata scheme of Zenodo repository.

2.4. Increased data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

This point is to be clarified during the course of the project, currently it is too early into the project to define the re-use of generated data. Depending on the data generated, this will be defined between the consortium members.

3. Allocation of resources

At the moment, there is no immediate cost estimated for making the data FAIR. Zenodo repository is open-source and completely free and the institutional repositories for storing internal data are also free of charge.

Albert Turon, the project manager of TREAL, will be responsible for the data management of this project.

For long term preservation, Zenodo has a lifelong retention period and hence there will not be any costs associated to this. During the course of the project, the consortium members will decide on how long the data will be stored in the repository.

4. Data security

All data in Zenodo repository are stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas stored in different disks. The servers are managed according to CERN Security Baseline for Servers (<https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure>). Internal data stored in institutional repositories are password protected and only those who are granted access are allowed to access the files. A daily backup of the stored data is performed.

5. Ethical aspects

At the moment, there are no ethical or legal issues concerned with the data sharing. If foreseen during the course of the project, this section will be updated then.

6. Other issues

At the current moment, there are no other issues to be discussed.

Annex 1

Work package 1:

Work Package	Data Set Reference & name	Data Set description	Standards & Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage and backup)
WP1: Thermoplastic specimen manufacturing	Manufactured and inspected test coupons: TREAL-WP1-D1_1_Manufacturing report	<p><i>Description of the data set:</i></p> <p>The generated manufacturing and inspection data will be included in the data set, divided into internal data (marked in brackets) and source data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spreadsheets (internal data) • Cad files • Inspection files • Coupons photos • Manufacturing and inspection reports <p><i>Nature and scale:</i></p> <p>The generated type of data will be spreadsheets, reports, CAD files and inspection images. The total size of the whole data generated should remain below 100 GB. The majority of the data storage will be taken up</p>	.xlsx .dwg .tif, .mp4 .jpg, .png .docx, .pdf	<p><i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedure, definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups</i></p> <p>The generated data will be shared between the partners through the Zenodo research repository. A closed access will be defined for the datasets and can only be accessed by the partners and the TM. The marked internal data will be stored in Zenodo, but it will be solely accessible for the generated beneficiary.</p>	<p><i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved</i></p> <p>The data will be preserved in the Zenodo repository until the end of the project, and then following the agreement between the consortium, the term may or may not be extended.</p> <p><i>What the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</i></p>

		<p>by the inspection files and manufactured coupons photos.</p> <p><i>To whom it could be useful?</i></p> <p><i>Possibilities for integration and re-use:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The data generated will be used among the other members of the consortium to integrate into other work packages such as WP2 and WP3. Scientific publications and conference proceedings generated will be useful for the scientific research community and industries. <p><i>Scientific publication?</i></p> <p>Scientific publications will be generated from the data obtained, but strictly following the dissemination terms and agreement mentioned by the TM.</p> <p><i>Information on the existence (or not) of similar data</i></p> <p>Data generated is completely novel and hence there is no similar data.</p>	<p><i>Identification of the repository where data will be stored</i></p> <p>The data will be stored in the Zenodo research data repository under closed access terms.</p> <p><i>Necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use</i></p> <p>All the generated data in this work package are in standard widely used formats, and hence does not require other tools for re-use.</p> <p><i>In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned.</i></p> <p>Intellectual property rights, breach of agreement with TM.</p> <p>Internal data sets will not be shared due to rules of personal data of the beneficiary.</p>	<p>Usage and preservation of the data in the repository is free.</p>
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Work package 2:

Work Package	Data Set Reference & name	Data Set description	Standards & Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage and backup)
<p>WP2: Test campaign for material characterization and design allowable</p>	<p>Experimental results:</p> <p>TREAL-WP2-D2_1_level_1_test report</p> <p>TREAL-WP2-D2_2_level_2_test report</p>	<p><i>Description of the data set:</i></p> <p>The generated data sets will contain the experimental results of the level 1 and level 2 testing. The following data will be generated and included in the data set. The data is divided into internal data (marked in brackets) and source data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spreadsheets (internal data) • Data text files • Test images • Test videos • Specimen photos • Damage inspection files • Test reports 	<p>.xlsx</p> <p>.txt</p> <p>.jpg, .png, .tif</p> <p>.mp4</p> <p>.jpg, .png</p> <p>.tif, .mp4</p> <p>.docx, .pdf</p>	<p><i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedure, definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups</i></p> <p>The generated data will be shared between the partners through the Zenodo research repository. A closed access will be defined for the datasets and can only be accessed by the partners and the TM. The marked internal data will be stored in Zenodo, but will be solely accessible for the generated beneficiary.</p> <p><i>Identification of the repository where data will be stored</i></p>	<p><i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved</i></p> <p>The data will be preserved in the Zenodo repository until the end of the project, and then following the agreement between the consortiums, the</p>

		<p>Nature and scale:</p> <p>The generated type of data will be spreadsheets, reports, test images and videos. The total size of the whole data generated can be roughly 100 GB, estimating 100-200 Mb of data for each specimen. The majority of the data storage will be taken up by the test photos and videos, and damage inspection output data.</p> <p>To whom it could be useful? Possibilities for integration and re-use:</p> <p>The data generated will be used among the other members of consortium to integrate into other work packages such as WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6. Scientific publications and conference proceedings generated will be useful for the scientific research community and industries.</p> <p>Scientific publication?</p> <p>Scientific publications will be generated from the data obtained, but strictly following the dissemination terms and agreement mentioned by the TM.</p>		<p>The data will be stored in the Zenodo research data repository under closed access terms.</p> <p>Necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use</p> <p>All the generated data in this work package are in standard widely used formats, and hence doesn't require other tools for re-use.</p> <p>In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights, breach of agreement with TM.</p> <p>Internal data sets will not be shared due to rules of personal data of the beneficiary.</p>	<p>term may or may not be extended.</p> <p>What the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</p> <p>Usage and preservation of the data in the repository is free.</p>
		<p>Information on the existence (or not) of similar data</p> <p>Data generated is completely novel and hence there does not exist similar data</p>			

Work Package 3

Work Package	Data Set Reference & name	Data Set description	Standards & Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage and backup)
WP3: Novel thermoplastic material damage and failure model	Material damage and failure model and validation data: TREAL-WP3-D3_1_Constitutive model	<p><i>Description of the data set:</i></p> <p>The generated data set will contain the routines implementing the material model and the results concerning its validation. The following data will be generated and included in the data set:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spreadsheets • Fortran routines • Abaqus files • Reports 	.xlsx, .txt .f .inp, .odb .docx, .pdf	<p><i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedure, definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups</i></p> <p>The generated data will be shared between the partners through the Zenodo research repository. A closed access will be defined for the datasets and can only be accessed by the partners and the TM. The marked internal data will be stored in Zenodo, but it will be solely accessible for the generated beneficiary.</p>	<p><i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved</i></p> <p>The data will be preserved in the Zenodo repository until the end of the project, and then following the agreement between the</p>
	TREAL-WP3-D3_2_Analytical model	<p><i>Nature and scale:</i></p> <p>The generated data will be mainly Fortran routines, Abaqus simulation files and reports. The total size of this data is estimated to be around 1 TB.</p>			

		<p><i>To whom it could be useful?</i></p> <p><i>Possibilities for integration and re-use:</i></p> <p>The data generated will be used among the other members of the consortium to integrate into the work packages WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP8.</p> <p><i>Scientific publication?</i></p> <p>Scientific publications will be generated from the data obtained, but strictly following the dissemination terms and agreement mentioned by the TM.</p> <p><i>Information on the existence (or not) of similar data</i></p> <p>Data generated is completely novel and hence there is no similar data.</p>	<p><i>Identification of the repository where data will be stored</i></p> <p>The data will be stored in the Zenodo research data repository under closed access terms.</p> <p><i>Necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use</i></p> <p>Most of the generated data in this work package is in widely used formats. Regarding the FEM simulations and Fortran routines, Abaqus software with a Fortran compiler will be required.</p> <p><i>In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned.</i></p> <p>Intellectual property rights, breach of agreement with TM.</p> <p>Internal data sets will not be shared due to rules of personal data of the beneficiary.</p>	<p>consortium, the term may or may not be extended.</p> <p><i>What the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</i></p> <p>Usage and preservation of the data in the repository is free.</p>
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Work package 4:

Work Package	Data Set Reference & name	Data Set description	Standards & Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage and backup)
<p>WP4: Parametric coupon models creation for virtual material and design allowable generation</p>	<p>FEA data: TREAL-WP4-D4_1_ FEAmodels</p>	<p><i>Description of the data set:</i> The generated data set will contain the FEA models for all targeted coupons and loading conditions as well as a validation report. The following data will be generated and included in the data set:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spreadsheets • Digimat analysis files (various extension) • Abaqus input files • Reports 	<p>.xlsx, .txt .mat, .vlp,inp, .pdf</p>	<p><i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedure, definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups</i> The generated data will be shared between the partners through the Zenodo research repository. A closed access will be defined for the datasets and can only be accessed by the partners and the TM.</p>	<p><i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved</i> The data will be preserved in the Zenodo repository until</p>

	<p>TREAL-WP4-D4_2_FEAmoelsValidation_Report</p>	<p>Nature and scale:</p> <p>The data will be mostly Abaqus and Digimat analysis files that are mainly readable text files. The total size of the whole data that will be generated is quite hard to estimate but we can expect it to be lower than 1TB.</p> <p>To whom it could be useful? Possibilities for integration and re-use:</p> <p>WP5 partners for UQ&M as variations around the data generated within this WP.</p> <p>WP6 partners for further integration in a global modelling workflow/platform.</p> <p>Scientific publication?</p> <p>A priori no scientific publications will be generated from this data (if excluding technical marketing material in scientific journal without peer review).</p> <p>Information on the existence (or not) of similar data</p> <p>Similar data should exist (within the partners & outside) for a sub-set of the targeted FE models. No public/shared info about the extent and validity of what may exist.</p>		<p>Identification of the repository where data will be stored</p> <p>The data will be stored in the Zenodo research data repository under closed access terms.</p> <p>Necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use</p> <p>Most of the generated data in this work package are in standard widely used formats. Regarding the FEM simulations Digimat and/or ABAQUS software will be needed.</p> <p>In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights, breach of agreement with TM.</p> <p>Internal data sets will not be shared due to rules of personal data of the beneficiary.</p>	<p>the end of the project, and then following the agreement between the consortiums, the term may or may not be extended.</p> <p>What the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</p> <p>Usage and preservation of the data in the repository is free.</p>
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Work package 5:

Work Package	Data Set Reference & name	Data Set description	Standards & Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage and backup)
<p>WP5: Uncertainty quantification and management for virtual design allowable</p>	<p>UQM data:</p> <p>TREAL-WP5-D5_1_virtual_design allowable_UQM</p>	<p><i>Description of the data set:</i></p> <p>The generated data set will contain the results of sensitivity analysis and generation of material design allowables of different tests. The following data will be generated and included in the data set:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spreadsheets • Python scripts (internal data) • Abaqus files (internal data) • Reports 	<p>.xlsx, .txt</p> <p>.py</p> <p>.inp, .odb</p> <p>.docx, .pdf</p>	<p><i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedure, definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups</i></p> <p>The generated data will be shared between the partners through the Zenodo research repository. A closed access will be defined for the datasets and can only be accessed by the partners and the TM. The marked internal data will be stored in Zenodo, but will be</p>	<p><i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved</i></p> <p>The data will be preserved in the Zenodo repository until the end of the project, and then following the</p>

		<p>Nature and scale:</p> <p>The generated data will be mainly python scripts, abaqus simulation files and reports. The total size of the whole data that will be generated is quite hard to estimate as the number of simulations depend on various factors. We estimate a rough approximation of 2 TB.</p> <p>To whom it could be useful? Possibilities for integration and re-use:</p> <p>The data generated will be used among the other members of consortium to integrate into the work package WP6</p> <p>Scientific publication?</p> <p>No scientific publications will be generated from this data due to the prior agreements with the TM.</p> <p>Information on the existence (or not) of similar data</p> <p>Data generated is completely novel and hence there does not exist similar data</p>		<p>solely accessible for the generated beneficiary.</p> <p>Identification of the repository where data will be stored</p> <p>The data will be stored in the Zenodo research data repository under closed access terms.</p> <p>Necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use</p> <p>Most of the generated data in this work package are in standard widely used formats. Regarding the FEM simulations and the scripts, ABAQUS software and python programming tool will be needed.</p> <p>In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights, breach of agreement with TM.</p> <p>Internal data sets will not be shared due to rules of personal data of the beneficiary.</p>	<p>agreement between the consortiums, the term may or may not be extended.</p> <p>What the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</p> <p>Usage and preservation of the data in the repository is free.</p>
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Work package 6:

Work Package	Data Set Reference & name	Data Set description	Standards & Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage and backup)
WP6 : Platform for generation of thermoplastic material virtual allowable	TREAL-WP6-D6_1_ Platform TREAL-WP6-D6_2_ Validation Report	<p><i>Description of the data set:</i></p> <p>The generated data set will contain a set of tools developed during the project or previously existing (e.g. part of partners' background IP) as well as report. The following data will be generated and included in the data set:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python files • Compiled code • Reports 	.py .exe/.dll .pdf	<p><i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedure, definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups</i></p> <p>The generated data will be shared between the partners through the Zenodo research repository, except concerning the compiled code being part of commercial products (e.g. Digimat). A closed access will be defined for the datasets and can only be accessed by the partners and the TM.</p> <p><i>Identification of the repository where data will be stored</i></p>	<p><i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data.</i></p> <p><i>Indication of how long the data should be preserved</i></p> <p>The data will be preserved in the Zenodo repository, except concerning the compiled code being part of commercial</p>

	<p>TREAL-WP6-D6_3_Guidelines Report</p>	<p><i>Nature and scale:</i> The data will be mostly reports and tools. The total size should be below 10Gb.</p> <p><i>To whom it could be useful?</i> <i>Possibilities for integration and re-use:</i></p> <p>Final deliverables so not to be re-used in another workpackage.</p> <p><i>Scientific publication?</i> A priori no scientific publications will be generated from this data (if excluding technical marketing material in scientific journal without peer review).</p> <p><i>Information on the existence (or not) of similar data</i></p> <p>Non existing with the targeted extend (capability & validation).</p>		<p>The data will be stored in the Zenodo research data repository under closed access terms, except concerning the compiled code being part of commercial products (e.g. Digimat)</p> <p><i>Necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use</i></p> <p>Most of the generated data in this work package are in standard widely used formats.</p> <p><i>In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned.</i></p> <p>Intellectual property rights, breach of agreement with TM.</p> <p>Internal data sets will not be shared due to rules of personal data of the beneficiary.</p>	<p>products (e.g. Digimat), until the end of the project, and then following the agreement between the consortiums, the term may or may not be extended.</p> <p><i>What the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</i></p> <p>Usage and preservation of the data in the repository is free.</p>
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Work package 7:

Work Package	Data Set Reference & name	Data Set description	Standards & Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage and backup)
<p>WP7: Project Management</p>	<p>Agreement reports:</p> <p>TREAL-WP7-D7_1_Implementation_agreement_consortium_agreement</p>	<p><i>Description of the data set:</i></p> <p>The generated data set will contain the implementation agreement and the consortium agreement signature. The following data will be generated and included in the data set:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports 	<p>.docx, .pdf</p>	<p><i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedure, definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups</i></p> <p>The generated data will be shared between the partners through the Zenodo research repository. A closed access will be defined and can only be accessed by the partners and the TM.</p>	<p><i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved</i></p> <p>The data will be preserved in the Zenodo repository until the end of the project, and then following the agreement between the consortiums, the term may or may not be extended.</p>

		<p><i>Nature and scale:</i></p> <p>The generated data will be text files. The total size of the data generated will be 100 MB.</p> <p><i>To whom it could be useful? Possibilities for integration and re-use:</i></p> <p>The data generated will be used among the consortium partners and delivered to TM.</p> <p><i>Scientific publication?</i></p> <p>No scientific publications will be generated from this data.</p> <p><i>Information on the existence (or not) of similar data</i></p> <p>Data generated is specific to this project.</p>	<p><i>Identification of the repository where data will be stored</i></p> <p>The data will be stored in the Zenodo research data repository under closed access terms.</p> <p><i>Necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use</i></p> <p>The generated data is of the widely used standard.</p> <p><i>In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned.</i></p> <p>Intellectual property rights, breach of agreement with TM.</p>	<p><i>What the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</i></p> <p>Usage and preservation of the data in the repository is free.</p>
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